

Sectoral brief

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Reducing Risks Together: Multi-hazards and multi-risks in the energy sector

Executive summary & Recommendations

The European energy sector is undergoing a profound transformation driven by decarbonisation, digitalisation, and decentralisation. However, this transition is increasingly challenged by the growing complexity and interconnectivity of risks. Climate change, geopolitical tensions, aging infrastructure, and cyber threats are converging to create multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios that threaten the reliability, resilience, and sustainability of energy systems across Europe.

The EEA assessment 'Adaptation challenges and opportunities for the European energy system' (EEA, 2019) warns that climate change and extreme weather events increasingly affect all parts of the European energy system. The most important changes include increases in mean and extreme air and water temperatures, and changes in water availability, extreme climate-related events, and coastal and marine hazards. These changes will affect the availability of primary energy sources as well as the transformation, transmission, distribution and storage of energy, and energy demand.

This document transfers the MYRIAD-EU approach to the energy sector, including harmonised definitions of multi-hazard/multi-risk, sets of historical events (MYRIAD-HES), and a multi-sectoral perspective (energy-water-ecosystems-transport-finance-agriculture-food). This approach is applied in

five Pilots (Danube, Scandinavia, North Sea, Veneto, Canary Islands) to co-develop Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) pathways.

Recommendations:

- Adopt and implement **integrated risk frameworks** that account for compound, cascading, and interconnected hazards, like ISO 31000, and leverage tools from MYRIAD-EU to assess cross-sectoral vulnerabilities.
- **Upgrade aging energy infrastructure** to withstand extreme weather events, including floods, heatwaves, and wildfires. Include **multi-hazard and multi-risk assessments** in these plans to ensure resilient and future-proof designs.
- **Extend cross-border interconnection**, which is a key strategy to strengthen energy systems against various climate-related hazards, and thereby reduces supply disruptions and imbalances (that lead to high price volatility and inefficiencies). It enhances regional cooperation, resource sharing, and grid stability, making energy infrastructure more resilient and adaptive.
- **Strengthen regional and cross-border cooperation** through EU mechanisms like the Risk Preparedness Regulation and Union Civil Protection Mechanism and develop joint contingency plans and shared data platforms for real-time risk monitoring and response.
- **Improve data collection and analytics** on energy infrastructure and hazard exposure to support advanced risk modelling by promoting open data sharing and collaboration between energy providers, researchers, and public agencies.

- **Training energy sector professionals** in multi-risk thinking, including compound and systemic risk scenarios.

Context

The energy sector is in a transition as it needs to decarbonise rapidly to help mitigate climate change. This transition requires reconsidering climate-related risks to the energy sector, with energy production becoming highly dependent on local weather conditions.

Example case

In the winter months of 2023–2024, the North Sea region experienced a prolonged **Dunkelflaute**, a meteorological phenomenon characterised by low wind speeds and dense cloud cover, leading to a sharp drop in both wind and solar energy generation. This event lasted several days and coincided with a period of high electricity demand, creating a perfect storm of supply shortfall and grid stress across countries like Germany, the Netherlands, and Denmark. At times, a MWh cost upwards of €1,000 was experienced – the highest price seen in nearly 20 years (Energy Exemplar, 2025).

The Dunkelflaute exposed the vulnerability of the region's increasingly renewable-dependent energy systems, which rely heavily on offshore wind farms and solar parks. With wind and solar capacity factors dropping below 20%, system operators were forced to activate reserve power plants, import electricity from neighbouring countries, and deploy demand-side management strategies to avoid blackouts. The event also triggered market volatility, with electricity prices spiking in Germany and plunging into negative territory in other regions shortly after, due to a sudden rebound in solar output.

This Dunkelflaute episode illustrates a **multi-risk scenario**: meteorological hazards (low wind

and solar irradiance), operational risks (grid imbalance), economic risks (price volatility), and strategic risks (energy security). It underscores the urgent need for long-duration energy storage, cross-border grid interconnection, and advanced forecasting systems to mitigate the impacts of such compound events in the future (Kittel et al., 2025).

The MYRIAD-EU project is designed to address the aforementioned challenges. Our vision is to catalyse the paradigm shift required to move towards a multi-risk, multi-sector, systemic approach to risk assessment and management. To achieve this, the overall aim is to develop forward-looking disaster risk reduction pathways in five Pilot EU regions: Danube, Scandinavia, North Sea, Veneto, Canary Islands. Within these Pilots, we assess trade-offs and synergies of various strategies across sectors. These sectors are: energy, ecosystems & forestry, finance, food & agriculture, tourism, and transport & infrastructure. Within the project, we develop tools and methods to allow us to better assess multi-hazard-risk within these sectors. The project is funded by Horizon 2020, and runs between 2021–2025.

Applications of MYRIAD-EU results

MYRIAD can provide stakeholders with a comprehensive understanding of how different hazards can interact and amplify one another. For example, prolonged drought conditions can increase the likelihood of wildfires, which in turn may damage transmission lines and disrupt power supply. Similarly, heavy rainfall following a wildfire can lead to flash floods due to reduced vegetation cover. Despite these interconnected risks, there is a noticeable gap in training and capacity-building programs that address compound, cascading, and consecutive hazard scenarios. This limits the ability of planners, operators, and policymakers to anticipate complex risk chains and design resilient energy systems accordingly.

Storylines were identified within the MYRIAD-EU project as an approach that could be used by decision- and policy-makers to gain insights into complex multi-risk systems, interdependencies between hazards and sectors, and the development of robust forward-looking **Disaster Risk Management (DRM) pathways**. In MYRIAD-EU, we have therefore adopted a definition of multi-risk storylines as: narratives of past or plausible future events to explore and characterise cause-and-effect relationships between risk drivers and impacts within a system. The approach follows five stages from defining the purpose of the storyline and setting boundaries, through data collection, analysis and synthesis into a final output.

Figure 1: Stages of multi-risk storyline development

The Scandinavian Pilot created a **storyline focusing on compound heatwaves and droughts**, which impacted Norway and more generally the Scandinavian region in 2018. The storyline details the direct and indirect impacts of this combination of hazards, also including wildfires. This compound event had a large impact on the energy sector, as 90% of electricity in Norway is generated through hydroelectric power. The Pilot’s work also considers spillover effects of hazards across sectors and regions. Their work, included in the storyline, highlights the importance of operational adjustments in the energy sector of the Scandinavian region. It also emphasises

the need for long-term strategic multi-hazard and multi-risk assessments implemented through a systematic, multi-sector, and multi-regional approach.

Energy sector decision-makers often lack access to actionable insights from research, and vice versa. MYRIAD-EU supports the development of forward-looking **disaster risk management pathways** that assess trade-offs and synergies across hazards, sectors, and scales. These pathways help energy decision-makers anticipate future risks and make strategic, adaptive investments in infrastructure, storage, and grid resilience. **The North Sea Pilot** has developed pathways for the nature, energy and shipping sectors and has looked into the cross-sectoral interaction effects of these sectors.

Figure 2: Systems analysis with plausible hazard events in the North Sea with climate change hazards.

Following from the sectoral understanding, the **North Sea Pilot** then developed first iterations of **sectoral pathways**, as shown in the figure below, spanning different time horizons depending on different socioeconomic-climate-scenarios and following certain narratives.

These pathways illustrate the strong interdependence and help to understand the driving mechanisms and qualitatively evaluate potential mitigating measures.

Figure 3: Intermediate pathways for energy sector

Recommendations

- Develop and use integrated risk assessment tools such as MYRIAD-EU's harmonised multi-risk model or DAPP-MR to assess how different hazards (e.g., floods, droughts, cyberattacks) interact and affect energy systems.
- Strengthen cross-sector and cross-border collaboration by establishing formal partnerships between energy and other sectors to share data, coordinate risk mitigation and ensure energy security.
- Train energy sector professionals in multi-risk thinking, including compound and systemic risk scenarios.
- Build and maintain multi-hazard datasets and vulnerability maps tailored to energy assets. Use dashboards (MYRIAD-EU dashboard) and decision-support tools to inform real-time risk management and strategic planning.
- Extend cross-border interconnection, which is a key strategy to strengthen energy systems against various risks, such as supply disruptions, demand fluctuations, and climate-related hazards. It enhances regional cooperation, resource sharing, and grid stability, making energy infrastructure more resilient and adaptive.
- Upgrade aging energy infrastructure to withstand extreme weather events, including floods, heatwaves, and wildfires. Include multi-hazard and multi-risk assessments in these plans to ensure resilient and future-proof designs.

List of resources

References

- EEA, 2019. Adaptation challenges and opportunities for the European energy system. Building a climate-resilient low-carbon energy system. EEA Report 01/2019. European Environment Agency, Luxembourg, <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/adaptation-in-energy-system>
- Energy Exemplar, 2025. Feast or Famine: How Dunkelflaute Impacts Energy Traders, <https://www.energyexemplar.com/blog/feast-or-famine-how-dunkelflaute-impacts-energy-traders>
- Kittel, M., Roth, A., Schill, W.-P., 2025. Coping with the Dunkelflaute: Power system implications of variable renewable energy droughts in Europe, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2411.17683>
- Penn, H., 2025. 2024 in review: The events that shaped short-term power markets, <https://dexterenergy.ai/news/2024-events-in-short-term-power-markets/>,
- Šakić Trogrlić, R., 2024. Challenges in assessing and managing multi-hazard risks: A European stakeholders perspective. Environmental Science and Policy, 157, 103774.
- Deltares. (2024). Final Report on Collaborative Systems Analysis and DAPP-MR. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16366175>

Other linked resources

- <https://blogs.worldbank.org/en/energy/building-resilient-power-grids--integrating-climate-and-disaster>
- <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/chapter/chapter-11/>
- https://www.efcanet.org/sites/default/files/2025-07/The%20Resilience%20of%20the%20European%20Energy%20System_LC.pdf
- <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/b2e7f93896d54574a79ab6f9801746fb>
- <https://dashboard.myriadproject.eu/methods/multi-risk-pathways/>

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